

Shakhrisabz state pedagogical institute
students Rustamova Sevinch Faxriddin qizi,
Norsafarova Zuhul Obid qizi

**THE MINISTRY OF RELATIONS WITH RUSSIA, THE KHAN OF
BUKHARA IN THE PERIOD ASHTARXONIYLAR.**

ANNOTATSIYA

In this article khan of bukhara, Uzbek khan who is from the beginning of the sixteenth century and during the period from the second half of the eighteenth century ashtarxoniylars dynasties of political relations, in particular, referred the word about relations with russia. In this period, khan of bukhara, the Russian empire, the ministry and the interaction of economic, political, cultural, and its place in the conduct of diplomatic relations, the ambassador also almashinilgan. By russia 1620, who came to samarkand in Xoxlovchi Ivan, and I sent in my liquor period in 1647 emperor pyotr gribov 1721-1725-years Benevini Florida is an analysis of the delegation headed by the goals and objectives of the mission.

Kali words: Imomqulixon, Xoxlovchi I., A. Gribov, People, F. Benevini, Pyotr I, stack.

To enter. Khan, who is one of the states of bukhara in central asia from the SIXTEENTH to the eighteenth century have conducted during the active foreign business. Ashtarxoniylar with their neighbors and bukhara began to build in the period of active economic, political, and cultural relations aimed at military targets in its place. Ashtarxoniylar by economic and political interests in pursuing the set of relations compared to the beginning of the eighteenth century later come to bukhara by pyotr pressure is equal to the state with the object of holding and conducted himself as discrimination policy shall be determined.

Analysis of the literature on the subject: Ashtarxoniylar khan of bukhara in the period's Russia muarrix about that period of relations with the ambassador of the current period, and the diary of the research of scientists can get information through. For example, scientists at the j. Uzbek barakaev "history of bukhara", don't zamonoviy A. "the history of bukhara khan", and n. h. sodiqov shokirova, prof. djurayev at "history of uzbekistan", rasulov a. and a. isoqov of "the history of relations and Russian Turkestan", R. alimova of "khan neighboring countries in central asia, as well as diplomatic and trade-economic relations are" relations ambassador in the book, referred the word about their goals and tasks. The main purpose of trade without stops to reduce the tax take from moscow and later specified that the central asian traders.

Analysis and results: SIXTEENTH-century central Asia and Russia in the sixteenth century was based on common interests and mutual relations. Russian rulers, from the initial times, in central Asia, in relation to the mutual relationships, as well as at peace with Khan, trade, led a policy aimed at the development of economic relations. However, from the eighteenth century, when the Russian state to consolidate economic and political aspects, south-east, began launching a policy of aggression. I particularly during the period of this management Pyotr begins to cast a clear eye.[1]

Imomqulixon occur until a development in diplomatic relations with Russia in the period. 1620 this purpose Khan-the King Khan Odambiyni year of Russian Mikhail Fyodorovich in the presence of a va sends. The king wrote a letter in reply to Imomqulixon Russian old friendship between the two sides established trade relations and cultural development act up thrived wholeheartedly tell o'the built in us. Answer as ambassador Ivan Xoxlovchi 1620-26-year-tiny approved comes with tabs to central Asia. Xoxlovchi in Samarkand in 1621, according to the commission, the meeting with the king and the Russian Imomqulixon, Ivan Xoxlovchi Russian Xondan asks you to do free shoots 27 units. Khan thus, while the response to the request of ambassador performs.

Khoja by another ambassador Imomqulixon Otaquli 1634-the king Khan in the spring of the year presented by Russian Mikhail Fyodorovich gifts and the letter will deliver. As a result of this meeting have the right to trade without the tax ko'browsing our can.[2] at an interval of ten years oshiqroq over time, that is, the Russian ambassador to Iran in 1646 by Alexei Mixailovich Gribovni my liquor king will send delegation visit. How to trade delegation to India from Astrakhan to go by way of convenience that Urgench, whether through the cities of Bukhara and Iran to know that you can go through or loaded. It is noteworthy to say that the king and the ambassador of the development of trade relations by a. identify ways Gribovga assigned the task of trading.[3]

Abulfayzxon I are dominated 1721 emperor Pyotr targeted on the basis of Bukhara in the period-6 years-in November, headed by F. Benevini will send the mission of ambassador. By F. Khan of Bukhara Beneviniga emperor / the condition of the castle, the structure of the army, the army of the total number of Bukhara state management method, and Iran, Khiva, Turkey's relations with Russia in the development of trade and to collect comprehensive information about the opportunities that are available, along with the identification of the gold reserves are entrusted to collect data about.[4] F. Benevinining 1721-1724 i.e. 3.5 years-the year of activity in Khiva against Russia in Bukhara-Bukhara, the organization of the

union,as well as how many soldiers in case war with the khan and the ball can be loaded into.Also,the khan of bukhara to the Russian abulfayzxon stack should be able to be offered and the political situation was spend studying.Florida Benevini hand under the mines under the guise of Hirot there are a few traders,and comes badaxshon balx to go. He practically ambassador F. Benevinining by vocation,works to deliver the collected data to petersburg dealt with.F. Benevini tasks effectively bajargach 1725-goes back to petersburg in [5].

Conclusion.If you have a long history of relations with russia and bukhara, during this period the local ambassador to moscow or petersburg, russia also sent from the ambassador of the mission of samarkand and bukhara. This is ambassador of the mission, the political relations,the development of relations between states in conjunction with the socio-economic impact in the field of their shows. Be due to the reduction of taxes and customs traders of central asia, bukhara began to come into europe and also in the Russian city begin free trade products.

LITERATURE:

- 1.A.Rasulov,A. Isoqboyev “the history of turkestan and Russian relations”-Namangan-2011.
- 2.A.Zamonoviy “khan the history of bukhara”-Tashkent-2021.
- 3.R.Alimova “khan neighboring countries in central asia, as well as diplomatic and trade-economic relations”-Tashkent-2017.
- 4.Djurayev N. H. Sodiqov “uzbekistan history”-Tashkent-2011.
- 5.A.Erqo'ziyev “khan the history of bukhara”-Namangan-2018.